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Bringing Outer Space Governance into the 21st Century

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Executive Summary

Humanity's use of outer space is changing rapidly. New technologies, more spacefaring states, and rapidly increasing commercial activities are generating numerous urgent challenges that current international space laws and institutions are struggling to address. Particular challenges include orbital debris, light and radio pollution from satellites, disputes over space mining, coordination challenges in Earth orbit and on-and-around the Moon, chemical emissions from launch and re-entries, and risks to people on the ground and in airplanes from uncontrolled re-entries of space debris.

The existing space governance system is fragmented and arguably out of date, including five multilateral treaties that are more than half a century old. There are numerous forums where international space governance is discussed, but limited progress is being made on addressing these challenges. States are instead pursuing unilateral and regional approaches, resulting in imperfect and limited measures.

This report comprises a literature review of existing research from the past ten years, including academic papers, government and industry reports, and other sources. It also identifies gaps in this literature and opportunities for future research. This report will assist the governments of Canada and the United Kingdom in policy development, diplomacy, and the allocation of research funding.

Key findings

- There are a wide range of proposals for potential changes to international space governance. Common suggested mechanisms include new international organizations, new treaties, changes to existing treaties, new norms, transparency and confidence building measures, and economic incentives such as funds and bonds.
- Common thematic areas include coordination on the Moon, space traffic management in Earth orbit, space security, and space mining. These challenges are emerging over different timelines, with some requiring attention now and others being more forward-looking.
- There is generally a divide between proposals for harder governance, such as developing new international laws and domestic regulation, and proposals for softer mechanisms such as voluntary guidelines and best practices. Proponents of softer mechanisms cite either the speed and flexibility of these approaches, the difficulty and cost of harder mechanisms, or both.
- The primary international organizations that could evolve their governance of outer space include the United Nations General Assembly, the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, the International Telecommunication Union, and the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee.
- Many international law proposals focus on the interpretation of the existing space treaties in the context of 21st-century activities. A lack of definition or specificity in these treaties is seen as a limitation, while others argue that it provides a more enduring framework for international space law because it requires—and therefore enables—further interpretation and development.

- The interplay between the security aspects of outer space, such as using satellites to enable precision targeting by military forces on Earth's surface, and the promotion of civilian uses of outer space makes governance more challenging. It is harder to separate civil and military uses of outer space than, for example, in international aviation or shipping.
- There is no shortage of proposals for changes to the international governance regime. However, a lack of collective political will is seen as hampering governance initiatives. Disagreements between states on the scope and mechanisms for change frequently disrupt efforts to enhance international governance.

Policy implications

There are many proposals for changes to the international space governance regime, addressing a wide range of challenges, such as space traffic management and coordination on-and-around the Moon. The feasibility of these proposals varies, with some seen as relatively easy to implement and others more speculative and difficult to achieve.

By prioritizing certain action areas that present immediate challenges, policymakers can identify governance changes that could help to address those challenges. However, a lack of political will continues to perpetuate the status quo, and states are unable to find areas of broad consensus. A longer-term view of sustainability, for both for the environment and industry, would help.

Key words: outer space, international governance, space law, space policy, treaties, satellites, space debris, space mining.

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Introduction

Rapidly evolving technologies and increasing numbers and types of space actors have generated numerous urgent challenges that international space law and governance are struggling to address, manage, and mitigate. These challenges intersect with escalating security issues as space continues to be militarized and starts to be weaponized. These shortcomings in international space law and governance have exacerbated adversarial relations between states. They have also allowed space actors to escape accountability for their actions. Without a reshaping and strengthening of international space law and governance, activities in some areas of outer space could be seriously jeopardized.

The governance of outer space – including international law and other forms of state-to-state cooperation, domestic laws, regulations and policies, and industry best practices – is slowly changing, but is widely agreed to be falling behind the pace of change in technologies and the use of space. Numerous methods of governance are available to different actors, and myriad proposals have been made to mitigate different economic, environmental and security threats. This report surveys more recent contributions, highlighting and evaluating possible options available to decision makers and identifying gaps for future research. By synthesising knowledge from academia, thinktanks, governments and industry, it provides an overview of space governance options available in 2026.

Governance proposals may be focussed on a single issue, such as space debris, or may span multiple issues. To provide the reader with an understanding of the various issues, section one provides a description of the cutting-edge problems as they stand in 2026, while section two provides an overview of current governance. Section three then evaluates governance options by type of intervention. Specific issue areas are invoked where appropriate. Throughout section three, a variety of sources are used, including academic literature, thinktank reports, government and industry reports, contributions to the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), and other sources. A significant focus is put on recent proposals addressing emerging issues, though longer-term issues and ideas are referenced where necessary.

Though not comprehensive, this report aims to provide policymakers with an understanding of the current evolution of space governance and potential options available to them to mitigate current and future issues.

1. 21st Century Challenges

Outer space is essential for the day-to-day functioning of societies and economies. Satellites support navigation, weather forecasting, banking, communications, food production, climate science, search and rescue, disaster relief, and military operations, among others.

The use of outer space has grown rapidly in recent years. In 2025, 321 successful launches occurred, up from 82 in 2015. Over 15,000 satellites are currently active in orbit, including two crewed space stations, and there is an increasing interest in the Moon and other celestial bodies.

Humanity's growing use of outer space is also exposing new issues, and with them, gaps in current international laws and institutions as well as national laws and policies. These gaps represent both challenges and opportunities; the following section aims to give the reader sufficient context to understand recent governance proposals.

Environmental issues

The amount of space debris in orbit, including discarded rocket bodies, failed satellites, and small pieces of debris generated from collisions and explosions, has continued to rise over seven decades of spaceflight. By volume, most of the debris has come from satellite breakups, including collisions with other satellites, explosions, or anti-satellite missile tests, though the largest pieces of debris are often abandoned rocket stages, of which there are over 2,000 in orbit. Active satellites must manoeuvre around debris, which means that debris must first be identified and tracked. The growing debris population puts safe access to orbit at increasing risk, as one collision could create debris that leads to another collision, in a cascade of runaway space debris.^{1,2,3}

Compounding this, the number of active satellites has dramatically increased in the past decade due to the construction of 'megaconstellations'—systems made up of hundreds or thousands of satellites working together in orbit. Filings made to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) suggest that over one million satellites could be launched in the coming years, though a figure of 100,000 is more commonly used.^{4,5} Most notable is SpaceX's Starlink, for which 11,000 satellites have already been launched. And in 2026, SpaceX announced plans for a one million satellite constellation for 'orbital data centres'.⁶ Other constellations are planned by companies and governments in the US, China, the European Union, Canada, and other states.

¹ References are given in full on first use, followed by author-title for subsequent uses. All references are given in full in the bibliography.

² Donald J. Kessler and Burton G. Cour-Palais, 'Collision Frequency of Artificial Satellites: The Creation of a Debris Belt', *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* 83, no. A6 (1978): 2637–46, <https://doi.org/10.1029/JA083iA06p02637>.

³ Sarah Thiele et al., 'An Orbital House of Cards: Frequent Megaconstellation Close Conjunctions', arXiv:2512.09643, preprint, arXiv, 8 January 2026, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.09643>.

⁴ Andrew Falle et al., 'One Million (Paper) Satellites', *Science* 382, no. 6667 (2023): 150–52, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi4639>.

⁵ Andy Lawrence et al., 'The Case for Space Environmentalism', *Nature Astronomy* 6, no. 4 (2022): 428–35, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-022-01655-6>.

⁶ Maia Davies, 'Elon Musk's SpaceX Applies to Launch 1m Satellites into Orbit', BBC News, 31 January 2026, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cyv5l24mrjmo>.

Coordination between constellation operators for collision avoidance purposes will be increasingly necessary. This ‘space traffic management’ is an active subject of discussion, with no easy solutions.^{7,8,9,10}

Satellites create both light and radio pollution, disrupting astronomical observations made from the ground or other satellites in orbit. Without mitigations, satellites visible to the naked eye could disrupt the use and enjoyment of the night sky by people everywhere.^{11,12,13} The arrival of megaconstellations has greatly exacerbated the issue and, without mitigation, could hamper space science as well as planetary defence efforts, i.e. the detection of asteroids on Earth-impact trajectories.¹⁴

Satellites and the rocket stages used to put them in orbit will often not burn up entirely during reentry into Earth’s atmosphere. Most reentries are uncontrolled, meaning the debris could land anywhere on Earth, creating risks to people on the ground^{15,16} and in aircraft.¹⁷ Preventing collisions between aircraft and space debris could necessitate airspace closures, which would in turn cause economic damage to the aviation industry.¹⁸

⁷ UN General Assembly, *A/80/20 - Report of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, Sixty-Eighth Session (25 June–2 July 2025)* (2025), https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/a/a8020_0.html.

⁸ Jamie Morin, ‘Four Steps to Global Management of Space Traffic’, *Nature* 567, no. 7746 (2019): 25–27, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-00732-7>.

⁹ Marlon Sorge et al., *Space Traffic Management: The Challenges of Large Constellations and Orbital Debris* | Aerospace Center for Space Policy and Strategy (2020), <https://csps.aerospace.org/papers/space-traffic-management-challenges-large-constellations-and-orbital-debris>.

¹⁰ Helen Weedon, ‘3 Steps to Improve Space Traffic Management’, *Space Data Association*, 13 January 2023, <https://www.space-data.org/sda/blog/3-steps-to-improve-space-traffic-management/>.

¹¹ Luc Riesbek et al., *The Future of the Night Sky: Light Pollution from Satellites* | Aerospace Center for Space Policy and Strategy (2020), <https://csps.aerospace.org/papers/future-night-sky-light-pollution-satellites>.

¹² Karlie Noon, ‘Thousands of Satellites Are Polluting Australian Skies, and Threatening Ancient Indigenous Astronomy Practices’, *The Conversation*, 20 April 2022, <https://doi.org/10.64628/AA.yk4rmyvdr>.

¹³ Karlie Alinta Noon et al., ‘Safeguarding Indigenous Sky Rights from Colonial Exploitation’, in *The Routledge Handbook of Social Studies of Outer Space* (Routledge, 2023).

¹⁴ Jeffrey Hall et al., ‘Light Pollution, Radio Interference, and Space Debris: Threats and Opportunities in the 2020s’, *Bulletin of the AAS* 51, no. 7 (2019), <https://baas.aas.org/pub/2020n7i097/release/1>.

¹⁵ Michael Byers et al., ‘Unnecessary Risks Created by Uncontrolled Rocket Reentries’, *Nature Astronomy* 6, no. 9 (2022): 1093–97, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-022-01718-8>.

¹⁶ Carmen Pardini and Luciano Anselmo, ‘Orbital Re-Entries of Human-Made Space Objects: Drawbacks for the Upper Atmosphere and the Safety of People’, *Journal of Space Safety Engineering* 12, no. 2 (2025): 274–83, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2025.04.009>.

¹⁷ Charlotte Hook et al., ‘Uncontrolled Reentries of Space Objects and Aviation Safety’, *Acta Astronautica* 222 (September 2024): 69–80, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2024.05.026>.

¹⁸ Ewan Wright et al., ‘Airspace Closures Due to Reentering Space Objects’, *Scientific Reports* 15, no. 1 (2025): 2966, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-84001-2>.

Rockets burn large amounts of fuel as they traverse the stratosphere, and larger rockets are being developed to launch more mass into orbit. The atmospheric effects of all these launches will likely be significant but are not yet well-understood.^{19,20}

Additionally, when satellites reenter the atmosphere and ‘burn up’, either in whole or in part, the resulting millions of metal particles may damage the ozone or affect Earth’s energy balance.^{21,22,23,24} This recently identified issue could require significant government responses, but first, more research is urgently needed.

Security issues

Outer space has long been used for military activities, including reconnaissance and communications.^{25,26} However, recent years have seen a growth in militarisation and the proliferation of counterspace capabilities designed to disrupt, degrade, disable, or destroy satellite systems. In addition, the US has recognised space as a ‘warfighting domain’²⁷, and it and several other states have founded ‘space forces’, distinct from air forces.

States continue to conduct relatively close approaches of other states’ satellites²⁸, and fears of adversaries acquiring technologies that could disable satellites have led to plans for ‘bodyguard’ satellites.

Jamming and spoofing of global navigation satellite signals (like the US’s GPS and the EU’s Galileo), which can disrupt civilian activities including flights and shipping, has become

¹⁹ J. A. Dallas et al., ‘The Environmental Impact of Emissions from Space Launches: A Comprehensive Review’, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 255 (May 2020): 120209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120209>.

²⁰ Martin Ross and Karen Jones, *Implications of a Growing Spaceflight Industry: Climate Change* (2022), <https://csp.aerospace.org/papers/implications-growing-spaceflight-industry-climate-change>.

²¹ Aaron Boley and Michael Byers, ‘Satellite Mega-Constellations Create Risks in Low Earth Orbit, the Atmosphere and on Earth’, *Scientific Reports* 11, no. 1 (2021): 10642, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-89909-7>.

²² Leonard Schulz et al., ‘Space Waste: An Update of the Anthropogenic Matter Injection into Earth’s Atmosphere’, *Advances in Space Research* 77, no. 9 (2026): 9589–616, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2026.03.026>.

²³ Daniel M. Murphy et al., ‘Metals from Spacecraft Reentry in Stratospheric Aerosol Particles’, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120, no. 43 (2023): e2313374120, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2313374120>.

²⁴ Patrick Flamm et al., ‘Space Sustainability through Atmosphere Pollution? De-Orbiting, Atmosphere-Blindness and Planetary Environmental Injustice’, *The Anthropocene Review* 12, no. 1 (2025): 140–47, <https://doi.org/10.1177/20530196241255088>.

²⁵ Bleddyn Bowen, *Original Sin: Power, Technology and War in Outer Space* (2022), <https://www.hurstpublishers.com/book/original-sin/>.

²⁶ Saadia M. Pekkanen and P. J. Blount, eds, *The Oxford Handbook of Space Security* (Oxford University Press, 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197582671.001.0001>.

²⁷ The Space Force, *Space Force Doctrine Document 1* (2025).

²⁸ Victoria Samson and Kathleen Brett, *Secure World Foundation: 2026 Global Counterspace Capabilities Report* (2026), <https://www.swfound.org/publications-and-reports/2026-global-counterspace-capabilities-report>.

commonplace.^{29,30} Despite harmful jamming being prohibited under International Civil Aviation Organization, International Maritime Organization, and International Telecommunication Union treaties, none of these bodies have been able to effectively deal with the issue.^{31,32}

Four states have tested kinetic anti-satellite weapons (ASATs) by targeting their own satellites with ground-based missiles: the US, Russia, China and India.³³ These tests created large amounts of debris that remained in orbit for months if not years, risking collisions with active satellites and crewed space stations. If more such tests occur, significant risks will be imposed on all space actors.

Cross-cutting issues

Interest in the Moon has returned in recent years, with the US Artemis Program, a joint China-Russia International Lunar Research Station and a number of commercially operated lunar landers under development. Some of these plans include resource extraction and utilisation, and there are competing views as to whether this is compatible with the Outer Space Treaty, which bans ‘national appropriation’ of the Moon and other celestial bodies. In addition to the Moon’s surface itself, considerable interest also exists concerning cislunar space – around the Moon.^{34,35,36} Activities on-and-around the Moon should be coordinated with others operating there, to reduce uncertainties or physical interference – including the lofting of lunar dust – that could lead to damage or military responses.³⁷

Asteroid mining has also been proposed, either for minerals valuable back on Earth or for water-ice that could be used to make fuel for space missions. In addition to the national appropriation issue identified above, asteroid mining could have a number of unintended consequences—including altering the orbits of asteroids and thereby creating Earth-impact risks.³⁸

²⁹ Chris Baraniuk, ‘GPS Jamming: The Invisible Battle in the Middle East’, Middle East, *BBC News*, 10 March 2026, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/c3eww1x9e1xo>.

³⁰ Kristin Burke, ‘Is Military Space-Based Jamming Normal? Some Worry It Is’, *War on the Rocks*, 13 November 2023, <https://warontherocks.com/is-military-space-based-jamming-normal-some-worry-it-is/>.

³¹ Marco Aliberti and Stephen D. Krasner, ‘Governance in Space’, in *Yearbook on Space Policy 2014: The Governance of Space*, ed. Cenani Al-Ekabi et al. (Springer, 2016), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-1899-3_3.

³² ITU News, ‘ITU Issues Warning on Interference with Radio Navigation Satellite Service’, *ITU*, 23 August 2022, <https://www.itu.int/hub/2022/08/warning-harmful-interference-rnss/>.

³³ Samson and Brett, *Secure World Foundation*.

³⁴ Aaron Boley and Michael Byers, *New Moon: A Cislunar Security Workshop Report* (Outer Space Institute, 2025), <https://outerspaceinstitute.ca/osisite/wp-content/uploads/Workshop-Report-on-cislunar-security-FINAL-2FEB2025.pdf>.

³⁵ Sam Wilson et al., *High Ground or High Fantasy: Defense Utility of Cislunar Space* | *Aerospace Center for Space Policy and Strategy* (2024), <https://csps.aerospace.org/papers/high-ground-or-high-fantasy-defense-utility-cislunar-space>.

³⁶ Charles Galbreath, *Securing Cislunar Space and the First Island Off the Coast of Earth* (The Mitchell Institute for Aerospace Studies, 2024), <https://www.mitchellaerospacepower.org/app/uploads/2024/01/Securing-Cislunar-Space-and-the-First-Island-Off-the-Coast-of-Earth-WEB.pdf>.

³⁷ Mariel Borowitz et al., ‘The Potential for Conflict in Cislunar Space: Findings from a Tabletop Exercise’, *Space Policy* 73 (August 2025): 101700, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2025.101700>.

³⁸ Daniel Deudney, *Dark Skies: Space Expansionism, Planetary Geopolitics, and the Ends of Humanity* (Oxford University Press USA, 2020).

Although the challenges identified here are real, serious and immediate, space has a number of additional aspects which complicate governance efforts. First, it is an area beyond national jurisdiction, meaning states must coordinate to achieve shared aims and unilateral action may have a limited effect.

Second, economic, environmental and security issues are often connected, making solutions harder to find. For example, runaway space debris could damage satellites providing missile launch warning or secure communications to militaries.³⁹ Failure to coordinate activities on the Moon could lead to conflict as well as environmental damage.⁴⁰ And the ‘dual use’ nature of many satellites – meaning they can be used for both military or civilian purposes – complicates war fighting and arms control.^{41,42}

Third, space is increasingly commercialised, and the emergence of powerful private actors has disrupted governance at both the national and international levels, with phenomena such as *de facto* occupation of orbits.^{43,44} On some issues, we now see corporate actors influencing norm development.^{45,46,47}

Many of the above issues, particularly the environmental ones, are caused by or are a symptom of the growing frequency of launches. More launches create more emissions from launches, and put more objects into orbit, causing more light pollution and collision avoidance challenges. They also result in more reentries, creating casualty risks for people and changing atmospheric chemistry. Yet satellites provide significant benefits, including through Earth observation, navigation and communications, that all states should be able to access. A careful balance of risks and benefits must be built into any governance regime.

³⁹ Joseph Imburgia, ‘Space Debris and Its Threat to National Security’, *Vanderbilt Journal of Transnational Law* 44, no. 3 (2011): 589.

⁴⁰ Timiebi Aganaba, ‘Only Effective Space Governance Can Prevent Future Conflict’, Centre for International Governance Innovation, 24 January 2024, <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/only-effective-space-governance-can-prevent-future-conflict/>.

⁴¹ Jessica West and Jordan Miller, *Clearing the Fog: The Grey Zones of Space Governance*, CIGI Papers No. 287 (Centre for International Governance Innovation, 2023).

⁴² Almudena Azcárate Ortega, ‘Not a Rose by Any Other Name: Dual-Use and Dual-Purpose Space Systems’, *Lawfare*, 6 May 2023, <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/not-a-rose-by-any-other-name-dual-use-and-dual-purpose-space-systems>.

⁴³ Mia M. Bennett and Zachary Cudney, ‘Holding up the Skies: Is Starlink Occupying Low Earth Orbit?’, *Territory, Politics, Governance* 0, no. 0 (2026): 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2025.2594491>.

⁴⁴ Christopher Johnson, *The Legal Status of MegaLEO Constellations and Concerns About Appropriation of Large Swaths of Earth Orbit* | Springer Nature Link (n.d.), https://link.springer.com/rwe/10.1007/978-3-030-20707-6_95-1.

⁴⁵ Anish Dey and Jithin Jagadanandan, ‘Balancing Commercialization and Sustainability in Outer Space: Addressing New Challenges’, *Acta Astronautica* 229 (April 2025): 895–900, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.02.010>.

⁴⁶ James Moltz, *The Politics of Space Security. Strategic Restraint and the Pursuit of National Interests*, Second Edition (Stanford University Press, 2011), <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780804780742>.

⁴⁷ James Moltz, ‘The Changing Dynamics of Twenty-First-Century Space Power’, *Journal of Strategic Security* 12, no. 1 (2019), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5038/1944-0472.12.1.1729>.

2. Existing Space Governance

Space governance is centred on international space law but also includes a number of international organizations as well as norms, guidelines, best practices and other interactions between and within states.^{48,49,50} This section outlines the primary elements of international space law as well as some of the other elements of space governance.

International law

Outer space governance occurs at multiple levels, including treaties and customary international law, norms of behaviour and industry best practices, reports and guidelines from international organisations, and domestic laws and regulations.⁵¹

Five multilateral treaties were concluded in the early years of the space age. The most important is the 1967 Outer Space Treaty⁵², which defines general principles for states operating in outer space—including peaceful purposes, non-placement of nuclear weapons, and a ban on national appropriation of the Moon and other celestial bodies. The Outer Space Treaty also specifies that activities in space must be authorised and supervised by states, even if that activity is conducted by a private company.

The Outer Space Treaty is elaborated upon in further treaties, including the 1972 Liability Convention⁵³, which specifies the liability regime for damage caused in space or on the ground, and the 1968 Rescue and Return Agreement⁵⁴, which specifies how states should treat astronauts found in their territories or stranded in space. The 1976 Registration Convention⁵⁵ specifies that states should register their satellites and other spacecraft with the United Nations. There is also the 1979 Moon Agreement⁵⁶, though it was only ever ratified by 18 states.⁵⁷

In addition to these treaties there are two relevant arms control treaties—the 1963 Treaty Banning Nuclear Weapon Tests in the Atmosphere, in Outer Space and Under Water (Limited

⁴⁸ Gershon Hasin, 'From "Space Law" to "Space Governance": A Policy-Oriented Perspective on International Law and Outer Space Activities', *Harvard International Law Journal* 64, no. 2 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4179934>.

⁴⁹ Daniel L. Oltrogge and Ian A. Christensen, 'Space Governance in the New Space Era', *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, Space Debris: The State of Art, vol. 7, no. 3 (2020): 432–38, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2020.06.003>.

⁵⁰ Jeffrey S. Lantis and Adam Bower, 'Mapping Outer Space Norms: A User's Guide for Norm Structures and Change', *International Relations*, 13 March 2026, 00471178261418898, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00471178261418898>.

⁵¹ Michael Byers and Aaron Boley, *Who Owns Outer Space?: International Law, Astrophysics, and the Sustainable Development of Space*, Cambridge Studies in International and Comparative Law (Cambridge University Press, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108597135>.

⁵² Formally titled 'Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies'.

⁵³ Formally titled 'Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects'.

⁵⁴ Formally titled 'Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space'.

⁵⁵ Formally titled 'Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space'.

⁵⁶ Formally titled 'Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies'.

⁵⁷ Oltrogge and Christensen, 'Space Governance in the New Space Era'.

Test Ban Treaty) and, to lesser extent, the 1977 Environmental Modification Convention.⁵⁸ Further to this, all activities in outer space are subject to general international law, including the UN Charter and customary international law, where relevant.⁵⁹

International organisations

Outer space security falls within the remit of the UN Conference on Disarmament in Geneva as well as the First Committee of the UN General Assembly in New York City. Since 1978, the Conference on Disarmament has been holding discussions on Preventing an Arms Race in Outer Space, though these talks have failed to lead to substantive outcomes.⁶⁰ Some of the problems encountered include disagreement on whether any result should be legally binding, the difficulties of verifying that space activities are peaceful, and related issues associated with 'dual use' spacecraft.⁶¹

Civilian space matters are handled primarily by the UN General Assembly's Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), which has both Legal and 'Scientific and Technical' subcommittees. Both subcommittees and the full committee meet annually in Vienna. COPUOS reports to the Fourth Committee of the UN General Assembly and is managed by the UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA).

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) coordinates the radiofrequency spectrum used by satellites and other spacecraft. The ITU holds World Radiocommunication Conferences every three to four years, where it updates its Radio Regulations—a treaty that provides the framework for this coordination.

The Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee was formed in 1993 and currently comprises 13 space agencies. Its non-binding 'Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines' have been updated four times since they were first published in 2002.⁶² In 2007, the guidelines were used as a basis for the 'Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space', which were endorsed by the UN General Assembly. Despite this, their implementation has been mixed, in part due to the costs that adherence would put on operators.⁶³

⁵⁸ 'Convention on the Prohibition of Military or Any Other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques'

⁵⁹ Ram S. Jakhu and Steven Freeland, 'The Relationship Between the Outer Space Treaty and Customary International Law', paper presented at 67th International Astronautical Congress, *59th IISL COLLOQUIUM ON THE LAW OF OUTER SPACE*, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3397145>.

⁶⁰ Paul Meyer, *The CD and PAROS - A Short History* (UNIDIR, 2011), <https://unidir.org/files/publication/pdfs/the-conference-on-disarmament-and-the-prevention-of-an-arms-race-in-outer-space-370.pdf>.

⁶¹ UN General Assembly, *Report of the Group of Governmental Experts on Further Practical Measures for the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space, A/74/77* (United Nations, 2019), https://www.outerspacelawsapienza.it/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/2.-A_74_77_E-FINAL-PROCEDURAL-GGE.pdf.

⁶² Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee, *IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines*, IADC-02-01 (2025), https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_12025crp/aac_105c_12025crp_9_0_html/AC105_C1_2025_CRP09E.pdf.

⁶³ Aliberti and Krasner, 'Governance in Space'.

The Committee on Space Research (COSPAR) was established in 1958 and focuses on advancing scientific research on outer space. It has also produced influential guidelines on 'planetary protection', which aims to prevent the accidental transfer of lifeforms between the Earth, the Moon, Mars and other celestial bodies.

The International Cospas-Sarsat Programme is a treaty-based search and rescue system that was created by Canada, France, the US and USSR in 1979. Satellites from participating countries receive distress signals from the ground that are then passed to the relevant national search and rescue administration. Although not well-known, the Cospas-Sarsat Programme has saved tens of thousands of lives. It is an international organization with its secretariat located in Montreal.

The next section of this report reviews several recent initiatives, not all of them successful, in order to show some of the recent dynamics of international space governance.

Multilateral arms control stalls

In 2011, the UN Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) on Transparency and Confidence-Building Measures in Outer Space Activities was established to reduce the risk of misunderstandings, mistrust and miscalculations.⁶⁴ Recommendations in the GGE's final report included information exchange on space policies, goals and activities, risk-reduction notifications, and voluntary visits to launch sites and command and control centres. However, these recommendations went largely unimplemented.⁶⁵ Further GGEs were formed on Preventing an Arms Race in Outer Space in 2018/19 and 2023/24; the former failed to reach consensus but the latter did adopt a document outlining potential arms control measures.⁶⁶

At present, outer space security governance is characterised by two competing perspectives.⁶⁷ Russia and China introduced a draft Treaty on the Prevention of the Placement of Weapons in Outer Space (PPWT) in 2018 and an updated draft in 2014. The US and Western allies objected to these drafts in part due to alleged difficulties in defining 'space weapons' and verification.^{68,69} Instead, Western states have advocated for the gradual development of collective

⁶⁴ Christopher Johnson, *The UN Group of Governmental Experts on Space TCBMs* (Secure World Foundation, 2014), https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/66dcc6872f6ed23bce1db235/6859b22aecc939d0f4c6f0d_gge-space-tcbms-fact-sheet-april-2014.pdf.

⁶⁵ Clemence Poirier, 'Persistent Engagement in Orbit: The Dark Future of Space Security Without Arms Control', SSRN Scholarly Paper no. 6534598 (Social Science Research Network, 7 April 2026), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6534598>.

⁶⁶ Louis Reitmann, *The History of PAROS: An Overview of Multilateral Efforts for Space Security* (Vienna Center for Disarmament and Non-Proliferation, 2025), https://vcdnp.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/VCDNP_The-History-of-PAROS_web.pdf.

⁶⁷ Zhou Bo and Wang Guoyu, 'The Future of Cooperation in Space: Irreconcilable Differences?', in *The Oxford Handbook of Space Security*, ed. Saadia M. Pekkanen and P. J. Blount (Oxford University Press, 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197582671.013.45>.

⁶⁸ Benjamin Silverstein et al., *Alternative Approaches and Indicators for the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space* (UNIDIR, 2020), <https://unidir.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Space-Dossier-5-Final3.pdf>.

⁶⁹ Adam Bower and Jeffrey S. Lantis, 'Contesting the Heavens: US Antipreneurship and the Regulation of Space Weapons', *European Journal of International Security* 9, no. 1 (2024): 1–22, <https://doi.org/10.1017/eis.2023.2>.

understandings – norms – to regulate military space activities by focusing on behaviours that can be regarded as threatening, hostile, or irresponsible.⁷⁰

In 2022, the UN General Assembly established an ‘Open-Ended Working Group’ (OEWG) to discuss ‘reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviour’. This focus on behaviour rather than technology aimed to bypass previous sticking points, and while the OEWG also failed to reach consensus, its meetings helped to advance security discussions.^{71,72} A second OEWG, on ‘the prevention of an arms race in outer space in all its aspects’, was established in 2025 and is ongoing.⁷³

Governance splits

In the absence of recent multilateral successes, some states are pursuing (re)interpretations of existing rules of international space law that favour their own interests.^{74,75} This is not unusual in international politics, but problems can arise when interpretations differ between powerful states or regional blocs, or unilateral initiatives impede multilateral efforts.

In 2020, the US released the Artemis Accords, a set of non-binding principles for development of the Moon, including the possibility of self-declared ‘safety zones’.^{76,77} As of May 2026, 66 states have signed the Artemis Accords with the US,⁷⁸ with China and Russia having notably not done so.⁷⁹ Instead, China and Russia are developing the joint International Lunar Research Station, along with 11 other states. A bifurcation of the international community over lunar coordination presents a governance challenge, with a recently established COPUOS Action Team on Lunar Activities Consultation (ATLAC) attempting to bridge the divide.⁸⁰

⁷⁰ Jessica West and Almudena Azcárate Ortega, *Norms for Outer Space: A Small Step or Giant Leap for Policymaking?* (UNIDIR, 2022), https://unidir.org/files/2022-04/UNIDIR-Space_Dossier_7.pdf.

⁷¹ ‘Open-Ended Working Group on Reducing Space Threats (2022) | United Nations’, <https://meetings.unoda.org/open-ended-working-group-on-reducing-space-threats-2022>.

⁷² Almudena Azcárate Ortega and Sarah Erickson, *OEWG on Reducing Space Threats: Recap Report*, 15 March 2024, <https://unidir.org/publication/oewg-on-reducing-space-threats-recap-report/>.

⁷³ ‘Open-Ended Working Group on Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space - (2025) | United Nations’, <https://meetings.unoda.org/open-ended-working-group-on-prevention-of-an-arms-race-in-outer-space-2025>.

⁷⁴ Philip De Man, ‘State Practice, Domestic Legislation and the Interpretation of Fundamental Principles of International Space Law’, *Space Policy* 42 (November 2017): 92–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2017.06.001>.

⁷⁵ Brian Israel, ‘Space Governance 3.0’, *Georgia Journal of International & Comparative Law* 48, no. 3 (2020): 715.

⁷⁶ Melissa de Zwart and Joel Lisk, ‘The Artemis Accords and Subsequent Developments’, in *International Space Law in the New Space Era: Principles and Challenges*, ed. Sandeepa Bhat B. et al. (Oxford University Press, 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780198909415.003.0012>.

⁷⁷ Ben McKeown et al., ‘Artemis Accords: Are Safety Zones Practical for Long Term Commercial Lunar Resource Utilisation?’, *Space Policy* 62 (November 2022): 101504, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101504>.

⁷⁸ NASA, *Artemis Accords - NASA, Artemis*, n.d., <https://www.nasa.gov/artemis-accords/>.

⁷⁹ Rossana Deplano, ‘THE ARTEMIS ACCORDS: EVOLUTION OR REVOLUTION IN INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW?’, *International & Comparative Law Quarterly* 70, no. 3 (2021): 799–819, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020589321000142>.

⁸⁰ Hasin, ‘From “Space Law” to “Space Governance”’.

In 2022, the US unilaterally declared that it would never again conduct a destructive anti-satellite (ASAT) weapon test involving a ground-based missile. Later that same year, the UN General Assembly adopted a resolution in favour of such declarations, and as of 2026, 38 states have made them. However, China, Russia and India (all of which have conducted such tests) have neither made their own declarations nor supported the General Assembly resolution,⁸¹ instead holding out for a wider agreement on rules concerning the placement of weapons in space.⁸² As a governance initiative, the US unilateral declaration was criticized for not securing similar concessions from Russia or China, thereby foregoing an opportunity to advance multilateral diplomacy.⁸³

2019 Long Term Sustainability Guidelines

The non-binding Guidelines for the Long Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities (LTS guidelines) were adopted in 2019, following nine years of negotiations at COPUOS.^{84,85} The LTS guidelines were a breakthrough in international transparency and norm-building; the clearest multilateral agreement since the 1978 Moon Agreement.⁸⁶ However, the guidelines are non-binding and national implementation has been slow and mixed.⁸⁷

3. 21st Century Solutions

As the rapidly increasing use of space brings new governance challenges, numerous experts have researched and recommended solutions. These include calls for new multilateral treaties and new international bodies, the involvement of non-state actors in space governance, and national rules that could be replicated and internalized by other countries. There have also, importantly, been calls for more research to be done on space governance due to the serious risks associated with some new developments.⁸⁸

This section assesses various proposals, focusing on those with the widest applicability.

⁸¹ Ching Wei Sooi, *Secure World Foundation: Direct-Ascent Anti-Satellite Missile Tests: State Positions on the Moratorium, UNGA Resolution, and Lessons for the Future* (2023), <https://www.swfound.org/publications-and-reports/direct-ascent-anti-satellite-missile-tests-state-positions-on-the-moratorium-unga-resolution-and-lessons-for-the-future>.

⁸² Hasin, 'From "Space Law" to "Space Governance"'.

⁸³ Michael J. Listner, 'Two Years After the ASAT Test Ban: A Realistic Assessment', *Global Security Review*, 9 May 2024, <https://globalsecurityreview.com/two-years-after-the-asat-test-ban-a-realistic-assessment/>.

⁸⁴ Peter Martinez, 'The UN COPUOS Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities', *Journal of Space Safety Engineering* 8, no. 1 (2021): 98–107, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2021.02.003>.

⁸⁵ Kyran Grattan et al., *Report on Implementation of 'Guidelines on the Long Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the United Nations Committee on Peaceful Uses of Outer Space' 2020-2022* (2023), <https://spacegeneration.org/executive-summary-report-on-the-national-implementation-of-its-guidelines>.

⁸⁶ David Kuan-Wei Chen, 'New Ways and Means to Strengthen the Responsible and Peaceful Use of Outer Space', *Georgia Journal of International & Comparative Law* 48, no. 3 (2020): 661.

⁸⁷ Grattan et al., *Report on Implementation of 'Guidelines on the Long Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the United Nations Committee on Peaceful Uses of Outer Space' 2020-2022*.

⁸⁸ Marco A. Janssen and Xiao-Shan Yap, 'Governing Outer Space as a Commons Is Critical for Addressing Commons on Earth', *International Journal of the Commons* 18, no. 1 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijc.1378>.

A new space treaty

Some critics of the existing space governance regime see the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) as an outdated agreement that fails to address serious new challenges. They suggest two solutions: update the OST, or create a new one.⁸⁹ In either case, updated text could clarify issues and ambiguities with the existing regime, in particular with regard to space traffic management and space resource governance.⁹⁰ The updated text could come in the form of an optional protocol – a separately agreed but supplemental agreement to the OST.⁹¹ The counterargument to this is that the ambiguity of the OST is what enables it to endure; (re)interpretation can help to address activities not envisaged at the time of drafting.

In any event, a new treaty is seen by many to be unrealistic at this moment in history^{92,93}, with the state-level appetite for OST amendments being limited.^{94,95} That said, an alternate view is that the COPUOS consensus model is reducing that body's ability to make progress on all but the least controversial issues, and that broadening COPUOS's engagement with outside expert views could improve its function, comparable to Arria-formula meetings held by members of the UN Security Council.⁹⁶

In the end, 'soft law' approaches may be more practicable and therefore preferable. These are norms or guidelines that exert some 'compliance pull' without being legally binding – such as the LTS guidelines or Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines.⁹⁷ Soft law has a lower cost than hard law—states may find it easier to agree to soft law because they retain the sovereign right to not comply. Soft law may be a stepping stone to harder law or, as a coordinating mechanism, a solution in itself.⁹⁸

An international organisation for space

There have long been calls for some kind of international organisation to coordinate activities in outer space, in the same way the International Maritime Organization (IMO), International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU) coordinate

⁸⁹ Imburgia, 'Space Debris and Its Threat to National Security'.

⁹⁰ Nick Storrs, *Outer Space Needs a New Treaty*, 05 2025, <https://www.taylorwessing.com/en/interface/2024/the-space-race/outer-space-needs-a-new-treaty>.

⁹¹ Paul Meyer, 'Could an Optional Protocol Be the Way to Stop the Weaponization of Outer Space?', *International Journal* 76, no. 2 (2021): 332–39, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207020211020521>.

⁹² Jason Krause, 'Rocket Law: The Outer Space Treaty Turns 50. Can It Survive a New Space Race?', *ABA Journal* 103, no. 4 (2017): 44–51.

⁹³ Israel, 'Space Governance 3.0'.

⁹⁴ James Vedda, *The Outer Space Treaty: Assessing Its Relevance at the 50-Year Mark* (Centre for Space Policy and Strategy, 2017).

⁹⁵ Chen, 'New Ways and Means to Strengthen the Responsible and Peaceful Use of Outer Space'.

⁹⁶ High Level Advisory Board on Effective Multilateralism, *A Breakthrough for People and Planet: Effective and Inclusive Global Governance for Today and the Future* (High Level Advisory Board on Effective Multilateralism, 2023).

⁹⁷ Joan Johnson-Freese, 'Build on the Outer Space Treaty', *Nature* 550, no. 7675 (2017): 182–84, <https://doi.org/10.1038/550182a>.

⁹⁸ Kenneth W. Abbott and Duncan Snidal, 'Hard and Soft Law in International Governance', *International Organisation* 54 (2000): 421.

maritime, aviation and radiofrequency activities respectively.^{99,100} The most commonly involved analogy is ICAO, which coordinates and harmonises rules for civil aviation throughout the world. In the early days of aviation, there were a range of competing proposals for governance regimes, but was only in 1944 that the Chicago Convention was signed and ICAO created; 43 years after the first flight. The existing space regime is somewhat similar to the situation that existed before ICAO; thus, the calls for an 'ICAO for Space'.¹⁰¹

Another proposed solution is that ICAO simply be extended to cover outer space.¹⁰² One argument for this is that it mitigates the issue of there being no legal distinction between airspace and outer space; if the ICAO were to manage both domains it could better coordinate between them.¹⁰³ Additionally, the Chicago Convention is more widely ratified than the five space treaties.

One challenge is that the distinction between civilian and military activities is more easily drawn for aviation than it is for space, where many satellites have dual civil-military applications or ownership. A further challenge is that any new international organisation would have to be grounded in a treaty. This might, in effect, involve revisiting the Outer Space Treaty, thereby encountering some of the same challenges identified above.

Norms and behavioural approaches

Norms can be defined as 'rules of behaviour rooted in shared values and societal expectations of appropriate conduct'.¹⁰⁴ If certain actions, or lack of actions, are sufficiently widespread they can be understood by parties to be 'norms' and not violated. Much like soft law, norms can, over time, become customary international law or lead to treaty negotiations, though this is not always the desired end point.

In the space context, there is a recognition that restricting certain technologies is difficult due to a lack of transparency as to what is being launched into space, a difficulty that is exacerbated by 'dual use' space technologies. Instead, certain behaviours can be identified to be destabilising—and states can refrain from doing them. The 2022 OEWG aimed to define such behavioural norms in a modern space context.

Many UN members states would prefer a legally binding instrument to address an arms race in space, while accepting that norms are a first step or that the processes are complementary.¹⁰⁵

⁹⁹ Dey and Jagadanandan, 'Balancing Commercialization and Sustainability in Outer Space'.

¹⁰⁰ Ram S. Jakhu and Joseph N. Pelton, 'Conclusions, Consolidated Findings, and General Recommendations', in *Global Space Governance: An International Study*, ed. Ram S. Jakhu and Joseph N. Pelton (Springer International Publishing, 2017), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54364-2_23.

¹⁰¹ Ram S. Jakhu et al., *The Need for an Integrated Regulatory Regime for Aviation and Space: ICAO for Space?*, vol. 7 (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-0718-8>.

¹⁰² Michael Chatzipanagiotis and George Kyriakopoulos, "'One-Stop Shop" Space Safety Regulation: Should We Do It and How?', *Journal of Space Safety Engineering* 6, no. 3 (2019): 212–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2019.09.002>.

¹⁰³ Sanat Kaul, 'Could ICAO Be a NewSpace Regulator?', *Room The Space Journal of Asgardia*, 2024, <https://room.eu.com/article/could-icao-be-a-newspace-regulator>.

¹⁰⁴ Jessica West, 'The UK Process on Norms and Space Security', *Project Ploughshares*, 6 July 2021, <https://ploughshares.ca/the-uk-process-on-norms-and-space-security/>.

¹⁰⁵ West, 'The UK Process on Norms and Space Security'.

The development of norms is an important part of space governance, though holding states accountable to them is difficult, especially in space where observation and verification capabilities remain limited.¹⁰⁶

Voluntary schemes and standards

Voluntary schemes involved non-binding commitments to improve safety or environmental performance.¹⁰⁷ They can include agreements, certification schemes or labelling. In the space sector, there are voluntary or non-binding schemes that are adopted by states, and there are industry or corporate level schemes that are administered by companies themselves. Non-binding measures and self-governance are often preferred by industry, for example, the Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices endorsed by SpaceX, OneWeb and Iridium in 2022.¹⁰⁸

There are a number of standards development organisations, including the International Standards Organisation (ISO) and the Consultative Committee for Space Data Standards, that can harmonise activities between states. For example, the European Space Agency requires contractors use standards from the European Cooperation for Space Standardisation (ECSS), which in turn references ISO standards.¹⁰⁹

Additionally, a number of organisations are developing sustainability ratings for space activities.^{110,111,112} These evaluate missions based on sustainability criteria and issue ratings or labels to incentivise more sustainable behaviours. While they are not governance tools themselves, ratings can alter operator behaviour or be combined with other measures such as insurance or bonds.

Broadly, voluntary schemes may have a limited safety or environmental effect. They are at risk of industry capture, may be poorly monitored, and might not be enforceable or transparent. As such they have to be carefully designed. Entirely voluntary approaches to governance will be limited in effect but might yield some positive outcomes or be a useful first step.^{113,114,115}

¹⁰⁶ West and Azcárate Ortega, *Norms for Outer Space: A Small Step or Giant Leap for Policymaking?*

¹⁰⁷ Marit Undseth et al., 'The Economics of Space Debris in Perspective', paper presented at 8th European Conference on Space Debris (virtual), Darmstadt, Germany, 20 April 2021, <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/proceedings/sdc8/paper/12/SDC8-paper12.pdf>.

¹⁰⁸ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices* (2022), <https://www.ascend.events/outcomes/satellite-orbital-safety-best-practices-by-iridium-oneweb-spacex-aiaa/>.

¹⁰⁹ Oltrogge and Christensen, 'Space Governance in the New Space Era'.

¹¹⁰ Adilov and Alexander, 'Engineering the New Space Economy'.

¹¹¹ Rathnasabapathy et al., 'Space Sustainability Rating'.

¹¹² *Space Sustainability Rating – Promoting Sustainable Behavior of Space Actors*, n.d., <https://spacesustainabilityrating.org/>.

¹¹³ Nodir Adilov et al., 'Earth Orbit Debris: An Economic Model', SSRN Scholarly Paper no. 2264915 (Social Science Research Network, 14 May 2013), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2264915>.

¹¹⁴ West and Miller, *Clearing the Fog: The Grey Zones of Space Governance*.

¹¹⁵ Morin, 'Four Steps to Global Management of Space Traffic'.

Economic proposals

Most economic proposals are focussed on disincentivizing space debris in orbit, including by reducing the chance of satellite breakups and increasing post-mission disposal (usually by deorbiting the satellite into the atmosphere at the end of its operational life). Some proposals seek to raise funds for space traffic management systems or ‘active debris removal’ missions to remove debris from orbit. It is possible to imagine these approaches being copied for other space-related environmental issues, including conducting controlled reentries or minimising light and radio pollution.

Space debris is mostly a question of incentives rather than technologies, meaning we have the capability to minimise debris, but do not currently do so.¹¹⁶ In an economic framing, space debris is a negative externality—it is not in operators’ interest to mitigate the issue as the future costs of damage or remediation are currently placed on others.^{117,118}

There is a recent and growing literature on market-based methods applied to the space sector, using lessons learned in analogous industries such as fishing, as well as with regard to greenhouse gas emissions. Market based methods aim to reduce negative externalities caused by space activities using financial methods, incentivising responsible behaviour without significantly distorting the underlying activity.

Taxes

Taxes aiming to influence behaviour, rather than raise funds, are known as ‘Pigouvian’ taxes, and have been proposed for space debris mitigation.¹¹⁹ For example ‘orbital use fees’, which are paid when an object is placed into orbit, have been modelled to reduce the number of objects in the space environment.¹²⁰ One argument for these taxes is that they reduce the future cost of inaction—by increasing the cost now, more expensive future debris mitigation is not required.

It is also possible that taxes levied on all missions could cover the cost of active debris removal missions for the satellites that fail.¹²¹

¹¹⁶ Akhil Rao et al., ‘Orbital-Use Fees Could More than Quadruple the Value of the Space Industry’, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117, no. 23 (2020): 12756–62, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1921260117>.

¹¹⁷ Adilov et al., ‘Earth Orbit Debris’.

¹¹⁸ Martin K. Zhu, ‘A Break-Even Analysis of Orbital Debris and Space Preservation through Monetization’, *Journal of Space Safety Engineering* 9, no. 4 (2022): 600–611, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2022.08.007>.

¹¹⁹ Adilov et al., ‘Earth Orbit Debris’.

¹²⁰ Indigo Brownhall et al., ‘Understanding the Effect of Fiscal Interventions on the Future Space Debris Environment’, <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/proceedings/sdc9/paper/237/SDC9-Paper237.Pdf>, April 2025, <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/proceedings/sdc9/paper/237/SDC9-paper237.pdf>.

¹²¹ Pierre Bernhard et al., ‘Large Satellite Constellations and Space Debris: Exploratory Analysis of Strategic Management of the Space Commons’, *European Journal of Operational Research* 304, no. 3 (2023): 1140–57, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2022.04.030>.

However, taxes are rarely considered a viable stand-alone policy response.¹²² Taxes have a heavy administrative burden and can be detrimental to competitiveness—both to other states and to other terrestrial technologies.¹²³

Bonds

Broadly, bond-based proposals involve an upfront cost to an operator that is then returned to them upon completing a certain behaviour such as deorbiting a satellite.¹²⁴ If the operator fails to conduct that activity, for example instead leaving space debris in orbit, the cost of the bond can be used to remedy the resulting issue (removing the satellite).

Under some proposals, bonds partially pay out if certain markers are reached, or involve variable costs—more risky orbits could be more expensive. Performance bonds such as these may influence behaviour more than a tax as they incentivise the desired action, rather than simply raising the total cost. The operator will receive their payment, plus interest, once they have successfully completed the desired action.¹²⁵

Bonds that pay out on successful post mission disposal have been simulated to increase post-mission disposal compliance rates, with even small bonds (\$100k) resulting in a 10% increase in compliance, though more expensive bonds have a larger effect.¹²⁶

Because such bonds, applied to satellite disposal, put a price on deorbiting a satellite, they create a market for active debris removal, which currently suffers from the issue of ‘who pays?’^{127,128,129}

However, one concern is that the bond only partially covers the liability and the government must pay the rest (for example, for an active debris removal mission). One bond was modelled at 5% of the satellite cost, approximately \$520,000,¹³⁰ which is an order of magnitude smaller than the cheapest active debris removal mission, which could cost between \$5m and \$100m per object removed from orbit.¹³¹

¹²² Undseth et al., ‘The Economics of Space Debris in Perspective’.

¹²³ Undseth et al., ‘The Economics of Space Debris in Perspective’.

¹²⁴ Michael Mainelli et al., ‘In-Orbit Servicing and Insurance Markets: A Symbiotic Approach’, paper presented at International Astronautical Congress (IAC), October 2023, https://www.longfinance.net/media/documents/Astroscale_-_Insurance_-_Draft_v10.0_Final_Copy_Edited.pdf.

¹²⁵ Nodir Adilov et al., ‘The Economics of Satellite Deorbiting Performance Bonds’, *Economics Letters* 228 (July 2023): 111150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2023.111150>.

¹²⁶ Brownhall et al., ‘Understanding the Effect of Fiscal Interventions on the Future Space Debris Environment’.

¹²⁷ Adilov et al., ‘The Economics of Satellite Deorbiting Performance Bonds’.

¹²⁸ Nodir Adilov et al., ‘The Economics of Satellite Deorbiting Performance Bonds’, *Economics Letters* 228 (July 2023): 111150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2023.111150>.

¹²⁹ Sammie Graff et al., ‘Economic Impact and Feasibility of Active Debris Removal: Initial Results from the OPUS Integrated Assessment Model’, preprint, 10 August 2025, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/394518822_Economic_Impact_and_Feasibility_of_Active_Debris_Removal_Initial_Results_from_the_OPUS_Integrated_Assessment_Model.

¹³⁰ Adilov et al., ‘The Economics of Satellite Deorbiting Performance Bonds’.

¹³¹ Graff et al., ‘Economic Impact and Feasibility of Active Debris Removal’.

Quality of government oversight and enforcement is critical to successful implementation; other industries have struggled with compliance and enforcement.^{132,133} A proposal comparable to bonds, except with a ‘smart contract’, has also been proposed, with the main benefit of this being the reduced government oversight required if there is a sufficiently trusted third party provider of data to verify the action has been conducted.¹³⁴

Space Debris Removal Insurance Bonds (SPADRIBs) have been proposed in the UK.¹³⁵

Insurance

Insurance has long been intertwined with space activities, with Lloyd’s of London underwriting its first launch policy in 1965. It was insurance underwriters which partially paid for the Space Shuttle to recover two communications satellites and return them to Earth in 1984.¹³⁶

The insurance industry could be a tool for governance, with an ability to rapidly adjust requirements for operators, though this is often as a result of a regulatory void.¹³⁷ Maritime insurance is one area that is comparable to outer space but considerably more developed.¹³⁸ This is of particular interest to the UK due to its dominant position in both the shipping and the satellite insurance markets.

However, the space insurance market has diminished in recent years, with declining premiums and most large payouts concerning launch-related or power supply failures.¹³⁹ It is generally agreed that the current ability of the insurance market alone to affect operator behaviour is limited.^{140,141}

There are also other possible mechanisms such as Insurance-Linked Securities (ILS), catastrophe bonds, or market share liability payments¹⁴², though these are less detailed in the literature.

Implementation of economic schemes

In the context of orbital debris, it is in the interests of all states to mitigate the problem. Economic incentives have been used to good effect— for example in fishery management, such as the Nauru Agreement on Tuna fishing, and emissions trading, such as the European Union’s

¹³² Undseth et al., ‘The Economics of Space Debris in Perspective’.

¹³³ Mainelli et al., ‘In-Orbit Servicing and Insurance Markets: A Symbiotic Approach’.

¹³⁴ Israel, ‘Space Governance 3.0’.

¹³⁵ Michael Mainelli, *695th Lord Mayor’s Space Protection Initiative (2024)*, <https://www.mainelli.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/2024.10-695th-Lord-Mayor-Space-Protection-Initiative-v1.0.pdf>.

¹³⁶ Mainelli et al., ‘In-Orbit Servicing and Insurance Markets: A Symbiotic Approach’.

¹³⁷ Andrea Harrington, ‘Insurance as Governance for Outer Space Activities’, *Astropolitics* 18, no. 2 (2020): 99–121, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2020.1786300>.

¹³⁸ Secure World Foundation, *Stimson Secure World Foundation Insurance Event (2018)*, https://www.stimson.org/wp-content/files/file-attachments/2018_stimson_swf_insurance_event_report.pdf.

¹³⁹ Undseth et al., ‘The Economics of Space Debris in Perspective’.

¹⁴⁰ Mainelli et al., ‘In-Orbit Servicing and Insurance Markets: A Symbiotic Approach’.

¹⁴¹ Secure World Foundation, *Stimson Secure World Foundation Insurance Event*.

¹⁴² Chelsea Muñoz-Patchen, ‘Regulating the Space Commons: Treating Space Debris as Abandoned Property in Violation of the Outer Space Treaty’, *Chicago Journal of International Law* 19, no. 1 (2018), <https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/cjil/vol19/iss1/7>.

Emissions Trading System.¹⁴³ These schemes are notably built on an existing international governance institution.

Economic schemes are unlikely to be a solution in themselves,¹⁴⁴ and good institutional governance is essential. Fortunately for space, good institutional governance is a pre-requisite for having the capability to launch and operate satellites. Economic schemes could then be added to existing institutions such as space agencies or airspace or radio frequency regulators. Once implemented, markets for active debris removal and on-orbit servicing are then created, incentivising positive outcomes such as post mission disposal and active debris removal. These mechanisms could lead to a 'circular economy' in space.¹⁴⁵

Any economic measure would change costs—startups may be reluctant to take on a bond, even if it pays back on post mission disposal, as they will have to raise more investment upfront. But these are costs that will ultimately be paid by someone, and managing them now is better, and cheaper, than dealing with them down the line. A well-designed solution would consider these secondary effects.

The challenge is to coordinate all this across the international community—economic measures must be implemented across all market participants so none are able to free ride on having less stringent rules and lower costs.¹⁴⁶

Spectrum allocations by the International Telecommunication Union provide an example of a market that is not functioning perfectly. The spectrum allocations are essentially given for free, but have significant value to operators, leading to gaming of the system, including hoarding or 'warehousing' spectrum.^{147,148}

Cooperative missions as catalysts for positive change

Numerous authors have proposed cooperative missions to build trust between major spacefaring states.^{149,150,151} There is a history of cooperative missions between states, even those which are adversaries. The Apollo-Soyuz docking mission in 1975 and the International Space Station, operating since 1998, show that states can still cooperate despite tensions on the ground. These initiatives require certainty and stability and are therefore often underpinned

¹⁴³ Rao et al., 'Orbital-Use Fees Could More than Quadruple the Value of the Space Industry'.

¹⁴⁴ World Economic Forum, *Financial Space Debris Mechanisms Workshop* (London, 2024).

¹⁴⁵ Nathaniel Dailey et al., 'Leveraging a Circular Economy for Space Sustainability: Government Roles and Economic Impacts', *37th IAA Symposium on Space Policy, Regulations and Economics*, 2024, 170–80, <https://doi.org/10.52202/078380-0020>.

¹⁴⁶ Hasin, 'From "Space Law" to "Space Governance"'.

¹⁴⁷ Nodir Adilov and Peter Alexander, 'Engineering the New Space Economy: Market Creation and Institutional Design', *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics*, ahead of print, 16 March 2026, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40812-026-00398-z>.

¹⁴⁸ Falle et al., 'One Million (Paper) Satellites'.

¹⁴⁹ Johnson-Freese, 'Build on the Outer Space Treaty'.

¹⁵⁰ Outer Space Institute, *Outer Space Institute Statement on Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities through Widely Inclusive Science Projects on the Moon* (Outer Space Institute, 2025), https://outerspaceinstitute.ca/osisite/wp-content/uploads/10_OuterSpaceInstitute_STSC2025.pdf.

¹⁵¹ Bo and Guoyu, 'The Future of Cooperation in Space'.

by international law; the ISS Governmental Agreement comprises 15 nations and has been in force since 1998.¹⁵²

If cooperation is deemed too difficult, coordinated missions may still be possible, such as the 1986 Halley Armada of Soviet, European Space Agency, French and Japanese missions to study Hailey's Comet.¹⁵³

Conclusions: Modern Governance

Governance requires an interplay between hope and realism. A better future must be imagined, but political realities must also be recognised. In outer space, it currently seems unlikely that a new general governance regime could be achieved. Instead, realistic governance proposals will involve a mix of governance approaches across various levels, including internationally, regionally, and nationally.¹⁵⁴ These approaches should draw from successful terrestrial areas of governance.¹⁵⁵

Policymakers should also be clear about the specific problems they aim to solve, and consider how these interact with other problems and solutions in outer space. As Jessica West has observed: 'The biggest question for the future of space governance is not who sets the rules, but what are the aspirations and outcomes we hope to achieve?'.¹⁵⁶

It is clear that there is an abundance of options available to the space policymaker in the 21st Century. However, to implement any would require the policymaker to break from the status quo. The question arises – why? Not why *should* they, which should at this point be clear, but why *would* they? The underlying issue is a lack of political will to truly tackle hard problems.¹⁵⁷ In many cases, space policymakers are not truly incentivised to deal with issues that will play out over decades.

Ross and Jones identify that the spacefaring states may be approaching a 'tipping point' with regard to space debris, where the costs of inaction become greater than cost of action.¹⁵⁸ The status quo could be disrupted by a change in public perception—caused by the increased visibility of space activities, or by wider environmental concerns.

Otherwise, a serious accident looks like the most likely thing to jolt policymakers into action, and states into cooperation. It could be a collision in orbit, or an uncontrolled reentry that strikes an

¹⁵² Joanne Gabrynowicz, 'Some Legal Considerations Regarding the Future of Space Governance', *Georgia Journal of International & Comparative Law* 48, no. 3 (2020): 739.

¹⁵³ Johnson-Freese, 'Build on the Outer Space Treaty'.

¹⁵⁴ Johnson-Freese, 'Build on the Outer Space Treaty'.

¹⁵⁵ A. Williams et al., 'Sustainable Skies and the Earth–Space Environment', *Nature Sustainability* 7, no. 3 (2024): 228–31, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01308-8>.

¹⁵⁶ West and Miller, *Clearing the Fog: The Grey Zones of Space Governance*.

¹⁵⁷ Frans von der Dunk, 'Structuring the Governance of Space Activities Worldwide', *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program: Faculty Publications*, 1 January 2020, <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelaw/113>.

¹⁵⁸ Ross and Jones, *Implications of a Growing Spaceflight Industry*.

airplane or a major city and causes hundreds of casualties. One hopes that a similar jolt would come from clear evidence that thousands of satellite reentries are depleting the ozone layer.

Absent a crisis of this scale, states should recognise that cooperation is both a goal and a means, and that tackling these problems is a form of leadership. For the UK and Canada, cooperating with other states brings both technical and governance benefits, catalysing the development of norms and helping to strengthen space governance for the rest of this century and beyond.

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